

Challenges before Objective History Writing In Modern Era

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Abstract:

Objectivity is the voice of history. In history, more emphasis is placed on facts than on personalities. In fact, by giving primacy to fact, we can protect historical objectivity. Historical objectivity can be postponed by practice rather than theory. Those historians are worthy of condemnation who distort facts or give importance to personal feelings. Historian should not give up objectivity and describe according to his personal interest. The impartial and independent approach of the historian leads him from one fact to another. Therefore the historian does not need to select the facts. The facts themselves pave the way for each other. The historian is only required to give respect to the facts while maintaining objectivity. Historians face the problem that they remain unbiased while describing the historical. In this research paper, the study of the problems faced in making history objective has been highlighted.

Key Words: Objectivity, fair and independent approach, personal interest and emotion.

The problems of historical objectivity are extremely complex. Historical objectivity can be recognized only after solving these problems by the efforts of scientific historians. At present, special attention is being paid to the need for historical objectivity, so that the study of history can be given a scientific form. In the absence of objectivity, it cannot be recognized as scientific. Before the inclusion of objectivity in history, it is necessary that we know the difference between general history and research history. General history can be objective due to being brief, but objectivity is not found in research history due to being detailed. In the first, the historian cannot use his personal feelings, whereas in research history, the scholar writer is able to select the fact and interpret it according to his personal interest and feeling. Despite the complexities of the problem of objectivity, historians have offered some solutions to it. It is true that historical details are not universal and timeless and are influenced by facts. The imprint of the personality of the historian is automatically visible on them.

3. Lack of Fairness:

According to Dardel's opinion, no substance itself is objective, but objectivity is established in it. Modern scholars seek to make history objective from outside disciplines, due to which the question of objectivity has become a matter of debate among scholarly writers and philosophers. To establish his opinion, the modern historian presents the description of the past in the context of a particular point of view, concept, culture, personal envy, malice or delusion, which is never fair. Because of this biased description, proving historical objectivity remains controversial among scholars.

4. Influence Of Social Environment

Karl Marx has considered man as a social animal attached to rituals. Due to the birth and development of history in the social environment, it is also influenced by religion and culture. Historian is also not free from these influences, so according to Marx, there is lack of uniformity in the description of Arab-Jewish, Hindu-Muslim and Russian-American historians. Therefore, historians who are supporters of the scientific method should try to find objectivity outside the society.

5. Change in History:

Undoubtedly, history is the study of the events of the past which have been presented by the historians of different eras in their own way. Mandelbaum also believes that the historian of each generation writes history according to the needs of his era. If slavery has been written as a boon in any era, it is currently considered a curse. Thus the very idea of scientific objectivity is a nightmare because of the variability of history.

6. Change In Beliefs:

Many authentic beliefs of the past have no importance at present. Similarly, the certified historicity of the present will also become meaningless in the future, while there is no change in objectivity with time. Arithmetically, there are always 2 and 2 make 4. Therefore, objectivity is always universal and timeless. In fact, scientific objectivity is beyond challenge, whereas the form of historical objectivity is not universal and timeless.

7. Age-Old Need:

According to J. A. Robbins opinion, the historian presents the collected historical evidence and facts according to the circumstances and needs of his era. Edward Meyer has written that, 'Contemporary social need has primacy in history

writing. ' The great philosopher Croce has also accepted history as contemporary and he believes that the human soul should be sensitive to its era, only then it can present the correct picture of the society in history. P . Gardiner has also mentioned that, the usefulness and non-usefulness of the same historical fact varies in different ages. Since the nature of interests and vested interests of human life has always been changing, the history of one era has been found to be different from another. Therefore, it is not possible to prove historical objectivity.

8. Impact Of Personal Emotion:

Beard has written that the approach of the historian in the selection of historical facts is influenced by personal feelings, social environment and circumstances. In such a situation, it is natural that historical rules are disregarded by him, due to which it is not fair to expect objectivity from him. Mostly the books of historians are inspired by personal feelings due to which historical facts are neglected and the effort of objectivity becomes almost dead.

9. Sense Of Prejudice:

Akashat believes that it is natural for a historian to be prejudiced. Often in history we study the side of the past. S. M. Trevelyan has mentioned on this basis that it is natural to have hatred and sympathy in history. The description done according to interest is not objective but subjective. Weber also says that finding objectivity in history is a flaw.

10. Selective Format:

Walsh believes that the nature of history is selective. Since it is not possible for a historian to describe the past completely, he presents only one aspect of it according to his ability. Being trapped in his prejudices, the historian writes the incident in his own way. Doctor . Ishwari Prasad and Dr. Agha Mehdi Hussain expressed conflicting opinion regarding the death of Ghiyasuddin Tughlaq. The first holds Juna Khan (Mohammed Tughluq) responsible for the murder of the Sultan, while the second holds natural disaster responsible for proving Juna Khan's innocence. So it is clear that the historian selects the facts in support of his opinion. This type of tendency is a great obstacle in the path of historical objectivity.

11. Predominance Of Feelings:

The writing of history is not rational but emotional. Renwef has written that, 'History writing is a matter of conscience. It is natural for him to be sentimental. Famous historian Gooch has also mentioned that the personality of a writer made of flesh and blood is expressed in the pages written by him. In which it will not be possible to separate the predominance of emotions and make them objective. Schiller also wrote that historical objectivity is a complex problem. Henri Pirenne has also written that no matter how fair a historian is, he

cannot be completely objective because the writer describes the events related to his own flesh and blood man.

12. Religion and Caste Problem :

Another problem of objectivity is related to religion and caste. Even if he wants to, the historian cannot free himself from the feelings of religion and caste. Medieval historians have tried to present historical facts arbitrarily due to the influence of religion and caste. On the one hand, if Sir Yadunath Sarkar has severely criticized Aurangzeb because of his bigotry, on the other hand, Farooqui has praised Aurangzeb highly because of this feeling. Similar sharp differences are also found in Roman Catholic, Protestant, Jewish and Arab historians.

13. Other Problems:

It is not possible for a historian and journalist to be objective. S. Dunner has also clearly written, 'The whole form of history may not be objective. Mandelbaum has also mentioned that historical justice is value-based, due to which it cannot be called objective. Social values always change. That which is not useful in the present tense does not necessarily mean that it was of no importance in the past. The historian cannot free himself from the influence of changing social values. Humans of a civilized society have relations with various political parties and the historian, being a social animal, is influenced by the ideology of the political parties and presents the interpretation of historical events according to his point of view. Therefore, it is unfair to expect objectivity from the historian.

Walsh has also written, it is as impossible for a historian to get personal bias out of his work as it is to get himself out of his own skin. In fact, objectivity refers to consensus and not the description of conflicting viewpoints. There is no difference of opinion in objective knowledge until the object changes. Objective knowledge is free from the influence of space and time. Yet, like scientific objectivity, the idea of historical objectivity is just a dream.

14. Conclusion

A learned historian does not present facts by distorting them as per his wish. His personal interest or isolation, biased approach and various theories also clearly indicate how the historian's approach maintains a relationship with objectivity. It is also mandatory for a historian to follow a certain code of conduct. In fact, in the absence of intellectual integrity, history loses its original character and becomes a novel or a work of fiction. The rules and discipline of history always inspire objectivity to the historian and the importance of historians like Gibbon, who ignore it, is gradually disappearing.

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